

Workshop: Modern Predictive Microbiology Analysis in R (PredMicro 2022)

Tutors: Ursula Gonzales-Barron and Vasco Cadavez

Invited tutor: Lihan Huang

27 – 28 June 2022

In the Framework of Partnering grants – GA 3 “Application of novel predictive microbiology techniques to shelf-life studies on *Listeria monocytogenes* in ready-to-eat foods (ListeriaPredict)”, funded by EFSA

(<http://www.ipb.pt/~vcadavez/listeriapredict/>)

Organised by: Food Safety and Quality Analytics (FSQA), Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança (IPB), Portugal

Programme (Time in CET-1)

27 June 2022

- 9:00 – 9:15 Welcome
- 9:15 – 9:45 Introduction to Predictive Microbiology. The Need for Predictive Microbiology. Classification of Models.
Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron
- 9:45 – 10:45 Experimental Designs in Classical Predictive Microbiology
Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron
- 10:45 – 11:00 Coffee Break
- 11:00 – 12:30 Statistical Analysis and Tools in Predictive Microbiology (I) - Primary Models for Growth and Inactivation
• Fitting primary models in integrated and differential form
Dr. Vasco Cadavez
- 12:30 – 14:00 Lunch
- 14:00 – 16:00 Statistical Analysis and Tools in Predictive Microbiology (II) – Omnibus Modelling for Static Experiments
• Fitting a mixed-effects non-linear (omnibus) model and validation
Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron, Dr. Vasco Cadavez
- 16:00 – 17:00 Experimental Designs in Dynamic Predictive Microbiology
Dr. Lihan Huang

28 June 2022

- 9:00 – 10:30 Statistical Analysis and Tools in Predictive Microbiology (III) – Dynamic Model Development
• Dynamic analysis and dynamic prediction
Dr. Vasco Cadavez
- 10:30 – 10:45 Coffee Break
- 10:45 – 12:30 Statistical Analysis and Tools in Predictive Microbiology (IV) – Dynamic Models for Microbial Competition
• Fitting Lotka-Volterra and Jameson-effect models
Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron, Dr. Vasco Cadavez

-----RStudio should be installed on your laptop-----